

Assessment of Drug Causality in Severe Cutaneous Adverse Reactions: A Comparison Between the Bégaud Method and the Naranjo Algorithm

Yasmine Mahdar

Dermatology department, Ibn Rochd University Hospital Center, University Hassan II, Casablanca, Morocco

Fouzia Hali

Dermatology department, Ibn Rochd University Hospital Center, University Hassan II, Casablanca, Morocco

Bouchra Baghdad

Dermatology department, Ibn Rochd University Hospital Center, University Hassan II, Casablanca, Morocco

Vigniako Roussaint Dossou-Yovo

Laboratory of Pharmacology, Faculty of Medicine and Pharmacy, University Hassan II, Casablanca, Morocco

Imane Rahmoune

Laboratory of Pharmacology, Faculty of Medicine and Pharmacy, University Hassan II, Casablanca, Morocco

Houda Filali

Laboratory of Pharmacology, Faculty of Medicine and Pharmacy, University Hassan II, Casablanca, Morocco

Hind Berrami

Medical Informatics Department, Hospital August 20, University Hassan II, Casablanca, Morocco

Mohammed Bennani Othmani

Medical Informatics Department, Hospital August 20, University Hassan II, Casablanca, Morocco

Soumiya Chiheb

Dermatology department, Ibn Rochd University Hospital Center, University Hassan II, Casablanca, Morocco

Abstract

Background: Severe cutaneous adverse reactions are rare but potentially life-threatening. Identifying the causative drug is crucial for managing and preventing recurrence. Two commonly used causality assessment methods are the Bégaud and the Naranjo algorithm, each with distinct approaches and limitations. The objective of our study is to compare these methods in assessing drug causality in severe cutaneous adverse reactions and to evaluate their concordance and practical applicability.

Material and methods: We conducted a retrospective analysis of 116 cases reported to the Casablanca pharmacovigilance center between 2019 and 2023. Drugs implicated were assessed using both the Bégaud and Naranjo methods, and their scores were harmonized into four categories: doubtful, possible, probable, and highly probable. Statistical analysis was performed using Jamovi software.

Results: A total of 442 drug observations were analyzed. Antibiotics were the most frequently involved drug class (34.5%). The Bégaud and Naranjo methods yielded identical causality classifications in only 37% of cases, with no statistical concordance ($Kappa = 0.062$). The Naranjo algorithm tended to

More Information

How to cite this article: Mahdar Y, Hali F, Baghdad B, Dossou-Yovo VR, Rahmoune I, Filali H, Berrami B, Bennani Othmani M, Chiheb S. Assessment of Drug Causality in Severe Cutaneous Adverse Reactions: A Comparison Between the Bégaud Method and the Naranjo Algorithm. Eur J Med Health Res, 2026;4(1):174-7.

DOI: 10.59324/ejmhr.2026.4(1).25

Keywords:

Pharmacology,
Pharmacovigilance,
Drug Eruptions,
Drug-Related Side Effects,
Adverse Reactions.

This work is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License. The license permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, on the condition that users give exact credit to the original author(s) and the source, provide a link to the Creative Commons license, and indicate if they made any changes.

implicate more drugs per case (median = 2.00) compared to the Bégaud method (median = 1.00; $p < 0.001$).

Conclusion: The Bégaud and Naranjo methods demonstrated poor agreement in assessing the causality of severe cutaneous adverse reactions. The Naranjo algorithm offers simplicity and rapid application, making it suitable for emergency settings with limited drug exposure. The Bégaud method provides a more detailed analysis, better suited for complex and polymedicated cases. Both methods have complementary roles, and an integrated approach may improve diagnostic accuracy in pharmacovigilance.

Introduction

Adverse drug reactions are harmful effects resulting from medication use, requiring treatment modification or discontinuation [1,2]. Among these, cutaneous adverse drug reactions (CADRs), refer specifically to skin manifestations caused by systemic drug exposure. Their clinical spectrum ranges from mild, self-limiting eruptions to rare but potentially life-threatening conditions.

Severe cutaneous adverse drug reactions (SCARs)—including Drug Reaction with Eosinophilia and Systemic Symptoms (DRESS), Stevens-Johnson Syndrome (SJS), Toxic Epidermal Necrolysis (TEN), and Acute Generalized Exanthematous Pustulosis (AGEP)—remain rare but pose a major diagnostic and therapeutic challenge.

More than 200 drugs have been implicated as potential triggers [3]. Early identification of the responsible drug is critical to avoid recurrence and to guide future prescriptions.

Causality assessment plays a key role in managing SCARs, but it is often complicated by polypharmacy, delayed onset, and overlapping clinical features. Two commonly used methods are the French Bégaud method updated in 2011 [4], which combines chronological, clinical, and bibliographic elements, and the Naranjo algorithm [5], a simplified questionnaire for estimating causality.

This study aimed to compare these two methods in the assessment of drug causality in SCARs, evaluating their concordance and identifying their respective strengths and limitations in clinical practice.

Materials and Methods

We conducted a retrospective **observational pharmacovigilance study** of all cases of severe cutaneous adverse reactions (SCARs) reported to the pharmacovigilance center at the Faculty of Medicine and Pharmacy of Casablanca between 2019 and 2023.

Cases with incomplete data and unidentified medications were excluded. Data processing and statistical analyses were performed using Jamovi software.

The diagnosis of SCARs was established based on clinical and biological criteria and systematically reviewed by dermatologists experienced in adverse drug reactions. When available, standardized diagnostic scores were applied, such as the RegiSCAR score for DRESS and the EuroSCAR score for AGEP, to ensure diagnostic accuracy.

To enable meaningful comparison, both methods' results were harmonized into four causality categories: doubtful, possible, probable, and highly probable. For the Bégaud method, intrinsic scores 10–11 were considered doubtful, 12 possible, 13–14 probable, and 15–16 highly probable. For Naranjo, total scores ≤ 0 were doubtful, 1–4 possible, 5–8 probable, and ≥ 9 highly probable.

Results

The pharmacovigilance center reported a total of 116 cases of SCARs: 58 cases (50%) were identified as DRESS, 31 cases (26.7%) as SJS, 15 cases (12.5%) as AGEP, 11 cases (9.5%) as TEN, and one case (0.9%) as an SJS–TEN overlaps.

The median age of patients was 39 years (range: 1–81 years), with a female predominance (63%). Of the 116 cases, 98 (84%) patients were hospitalized, while 18 (16%) were managed without hospitalization.

A total of 442 drugs were reported across all cases, with a median of 3 drugs per patient (range: 1–11). Antibiotics were the most frequently implicated drug class, accounting for 34.5% of the cases.

Causality assessment using the French and Naranjo methods yielded identical results in 164 out of 442 drug observations (37%). However, no concordance was observed between the two methods (**Table 1**).

Table 1: Concordance between the French and Naranjo Causality Assessment Methods

The Bégaud method	Naranjo score			Kappa coefficient
	Doubtful	Possible	Probable	
Doubtful	11	7	4	0,062
Possible	1	13	63	
Probable	0	17	140	
Highly probable	0	6	180	

A statistically significant difference was found in the number of drugs considered as suspected agents by each method, with a median of 1.00 drug per case using the French method versus 2.00 with the Naranjo algorithm ($p < 0.001$).

Discussion

Our study highlights the complexity of assessing drug causality in severe cutaneous adverse reactions (SCARs), particularly in the context of polypharmacy and heterogeneous clinical presentations.

It is difficult to achieve concordant causality scores when applying different methods. This underlines the crucial importance of providing clear, objective, and highly relevant information when reporting adverse drug reactions. Moreover, comparisons between different observers using the same method have also shown substantial variability in scoring.

Although both the Bégau method and the Naranjo algorithm are widely accepted tools for assessing drug causality, our study revealed a marked lack of concordance between them. Among the 442 drug evaluations, only 37% produced identical results, with a very weak statistical agreement (Kappa coefficient = 0.062), highlighting the divergent principles underlying each method. These findings align with previous reports showing limited consistency between structured algorithms and expert-based assessments [6]. Similarly, no concordance was observed in our series, corroborating the results of Eiden et al. in their analysis of voriconazole-related adverse events [7].

The French method, grounded in chronological, semiological, and bibliographic criteria, benefits from algorithmic rigor and discriminating bibliographic weighting. It enables detailed analysis, especially useful in complex situations involving multiple drugs or unclear drug exposure timelines. Nevertheless, it has limitations, notably significant inter-observer variability and sometimes uncertain scoring, with reported reliability varying from 68% to 98% [8,9].

On the other hand, the Naranjo algorithm provides a rapid, accessible, and internationally recognized approach. Its questionnaire-based structure allows quick application, making it particularly useful in emergency contexts. However, its utility decreases when multiple drugs are involved, as it tends to attribute causality to more than one agent, as observed in our study (median of 2.00 suspected drugs per case with Naranjo vs. 1.00 with the French method, $p < 0.001$). Furthermore, it relies on clinical parameters like drug re-challenge, which are often unethical or impractical in SCARs. Its sensitivity and negative predictive value are also limited for specific reactions such as hepatotoxicity [6,8,10].

Conclusion

Our study confirmed a lack of concordance between the Bégau and Naranjo methods, reflecting their different underlying approaches. The Naranjo algorithm is simple and fast, making it suitable for emergency settings or cases involving few medications. Conversely, the Bégau method, though more time-consuming and requiring bibliographic support, provides a more detailed and robust assessment, especially useful in polymedicated patients or when drug discontinuation is incomplete. Given their complementary strengths, combining these tools or developing integrated methods could improve the accuracy and consistency of causality assessment in pharmacovigilance practice.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

Funding

The authors declare no relevant financial or non-financial interests.

References

- [1] Montastruc JL. Pharmacovigilance and drug safety: fair prescribing and clinical research. *Thérapie*. 2022;77(3):261–263. doi:10.1016/j.therap.2022.03.001
- [2] Edwards IR, Aronson JK. Adverse drug reactions: definitions, diagnosis, and management. *Lancet*. 2000 Oct 7;356(9237):1255–1259. doi:10.1016/S0140-6736(00)02799-9
- [3] Grover S. Severe cutaneous adverse reactions. *Indian J Dermatol Venereol Leprol*. 2011;77(1):3.
- [4] Arimone Y, Bégau B, Miremont-Salamé G, et al. Updating the French method for imputability of adverse drug reactions. *Thérapie*. 2011;66(5):517–525. doi:10.2515/therapie/2011048
- [5] Naranjo CA, Busto U, Sellers EM, et al. A method for estimating the probability of adverse drug reactions. *Clin Pharmacol Ther*. 1981;30(2):239–245. doi:10.1038/clpt.1981.154
- [6] Seger D, Barker K, McNaughton C. Misuse of the Naranjo Adverse Drug Reaction Probability Scale in toxicology. *Clin Toxicol (Phila)*. 2013;51(6):461–466. doi:10.3109/15563650.2013.811588
- [7] Eiden C, Peyrière H. Comparaison de deux méthodes d'imputabilité des effets indésirables du voriconazole notifiés dans la base nationale de pharmacovigilance: Bégau versus Naranjo. *Pharm Hosp*. 2009;44(4):186–189.
- [8] Agbabiaka TB, Savović J, Ernst E. Methods for causality assessment of adverse drug reactions. *Drug Saf*. 2008;31(1):21–37. doi:10.2165/00002018-200831010-00003

[9] Gourier G, Ingen-Housz-Oro S, Sanchez-Pena P, Lebrun-Vignes B. Évaluation de l'imputabilité médicamenteuse devant une suspicion de toxidermie. *Ann Dermatol Venereol – FMC*. 2023;3(6):399–410.

[10] Murali M, Suppes SL, Feldman K, Goldman JL. Utilization of the Naranjo scale to evaluate adverse drug reactions at a free-standing children's hospital. *PLoS One*. 2021;16(1):e0245368. doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0245368

